
A CRITICAL REVIEW ON THE CONCEPT OF ECO-FRIENDLY LIBRARY

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Abstract:

Green concept has become a trendy discussion not only among the library professionals but also in other fields like veterinary medicine, health, agro-chemicals, pharmacy etc. Besides other countries have taken better solution India is doing well as par. Therefore, the purpose of this article is to develop awareness among the researchers and library science members the importance of green and sustainable development in the domain of library.

Keywords: *Eco-friendly, Renewable, Green building, Energy conservation, Green Practices*

Introduction:

A library is the organized collection of information resources made accessible to a definite community for reference or borrowing and the place for collection of these resources is known as library[1]. The library concept dates back millennia. The word library is derived from the Latin word liber, which means book. The first systematically organized library in the ancient middle east was established in the 7th century BC by Assyrian rulers in present provinces of Iran. For the historical concepts it is defined as places to keep business, legal, historical and religious records of a civilization[2]. The libraries have emerged since the middle of 20th century as a far reaching body of information resources and service that do not even require the building.

There is continuous changes and development in the domain of library [3]. The rapid development in the computers,

telecommunications and other technologies have made it possible to store and retrieve information in many different forms and from any place with a computer and telephone connection. The term digital library and virtual library are used to indicate vast collection of information to which people gain access over internet, cable television or some other type of remote electronic connections [5]. In early day libraries were involved in exploiting information technologies. For several year libraries have participated in co-operative venture with other libraries [6]. As libraries have changed, so , too , has the role of librarian. Thus, librarian have assumed the role of educator to teach their users how to find information both in library and over electronic network. The work of librarian has also moved outside the library walls. Librarians have begun to work in the information industry as salespeople, designers of new information

systems, researchers and information analyst [7].

Green Library:

It has something to be wondered, in this information and technology seeking era why it is necessary to discuss and go back to the stone age in which period of time the whole life of human beings fully dependent on the environment. Not only Indian, but the whole faces the problem of environmental issues with the rapid change of modern technology. Today the word 'Green' has become very popular among researchers, academicians and industrialists. The 'Green' concept is rapidly emerging in different areas such as Green chemistry, Green Nanotechnology, Green Synthesis and so on. The green movement is very much concerned with global warming. Libraries are considered as the place of lifelong learning and provide users required knowledge. According to the dictionary 'Green library or sustainable library is defined as a library designed to minimize the negative impact on the natural environment and maximize indoor environmental quality by means of careful site selection, use of natural construction materials and biodegradable products, conservation of sources like

water, energy, paper and responsible waste disposable recycling etc.

Measures to Implement Green Concept:

The green initiatives suggest four major steps that can be integrated in the library landscape to develop an effective green library. Green or sustainable libraries are the structure that is designed, built, revolted, operated or reused in an ecological and resource efficient manner. Green library concept includes various areas of sustainability as a multifaceted concept as mentioned below:

- Green library building
- Green library practice and operations
- Green collection development and literacy program
- Smart and innovative technology for green technology
- Energy conservation practices

The design and Development of Library Building with Green Approach:

With the intellectual design and proper architecture it is possible to develop the library building with green approaches. The possible initiatives for the development of green building for library are furnished as below:

Design and Development of Green Building

Serial No	Green Approach	Benefits
1	Airtight construction	Restricts dust, pollutants, smokes and allows free air in the building
2	Building materials made from recycled and renewable materials	Saves natural resources and reduces pollution
3	Properly designed ventilated system	Ensures air regulation, controls impurities, reduces room temperature, control humidity levels and reduces energy issue
4	Rooftop garden	Reduces heat of the building, maintains building temperature and removes carbon dioxide
5	Solar panels	Libraries can use renewable energy to meet their electricity requirements and act as role model for others

6	Use of LED lights	LED lights are more efficient and utilizes less energy than conventional lightening, low heat radiation, high brightness and longer life
7	Use of soft pads in chairs	With the use of acoustic controls, soft pads are being used over the feet of the chairs to reduce noise pollution
8	Use of sensor taps and dust-flush toilets	Decreases water uses in bathrooms
9	Tree plantation	The plantation of trees prevent pollution and increases the aesthetic appeal of life

Modern Technological Approach for the development of Green library:

- **Solar panels:** The solar panel, solar cells, photo-voltaic modules are assembly of photo-voltaic cells. The solar panels are used to generate electricity. This is the economic and eco-friendly way to generate the electricity. The array of photovoltaic cells supplies solar electricity to electrical equipment. The solar panels can be fixed on the roof of library which can generate the electricity required in the library.
- **Automatic Lightening control systems:** This is an effective strategy that significantly promotes energy savings. The amount of available light adjusts according to the space oriented.
- **Indoor air quality monitoring:** The indoor air quality monitoring or testing is an essential process to determine the level of contaminants present in indoor air which can affect productivity and well-being of occupants. The good and healthy air quality at workplace can increase worker's efficiency, improve health conditions and keeps mind good. The indoor quality includes percentage of carbon di-oxide, carbon monoxide, particulate

matters etc. According to EPA, common indoor pollutants are high moisture, volatile organic compounds, combustion products, radon, pesticides, dust particles, virus and bacteria.

- **Monitor sensor Devices:** We commonly observe that many times the visitors do not switch off the light or fan before leaving the place and thus wastage of electricity takes place. It is possible to detect presence or absence of the readers with help of a motion sensor device. Such type of devices are already being used in some international libraries such as National Library Singapore.
- **Water conservation:** In the urinal or toilet there is wastage of water during the flush. Therefore, there is auto flush system, where the flush detects and can discharge water till complete wash. Also the sensors can be used in drinking water place. This will save water and energy.
- **Waste Management:** Library is the rich source of books, periodicals, new papers, manuscripts and books. The newspapers, periodicals and sometimes books after certain period is to be discarded. Many times the answer sheets disposal is

important point of consideration. Many organizations burn the answer sheets. This creates air pollution. Therefore, different measures can be implemented under green library policy. One of the measure is the recycling. Here the answer papers are cut into small pieces and again recycled. This will save the earth and ready pulp will be available for use again.

- **Green program and services:**

Green concept pushes the libraries to offer green library service in addition to the sustainable construction and buildings. The green message should be transferred to the society through various programs like workshops, seminars and create awareness among researchers. The green library and green education policy play a major role to reach the ultimate goal of green world. The library can launch some efficient programs.

Conclusion:

The concept of green library is becoming popular and gaining importance day by day. The introduction of green library will be eco- friendly, save energy and healthy. We hope in future every library will adopt this phenomenon. This will be useful to control green house effect and global warming.

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